

Reaction of heart rate variability on orthostatic load in elite athletes

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Abstract

One of the most important components of the functional state of the athlete's body is the system of autonomic regulation of the heart rate. More informative and safe method is the load with orthostatic changes. The purpose: study is to study the characteristics of the heart rate variability response to orthostatic load in elite athletes. The study involved 26 elite Greco-Roman wrestlers. Heart rate was recorded using a Polar RS800CX cardiomonitor during active orthostatic load. The studies were conducted in two positions: horizontal (5 min heart rate recording) and vertical (5 min heart rate recording). Heart rate variability data were calculated using the Kubios HRV statistical program. Orthostatic load is a convenient model of the adaptation process for studying the transient process of heart rate fluctuations in athletes. The study showed the predominance of the sympathetic tone of the autonomic regulation of the heart rate in athletes with an optimal and low degree of stress response to orthostatic load. It was noted that athletes with an optimal and low degree of stress response to orthostatic load have a predominance of the LF power of heart rate variability. A tendency to decrease in SD1 and SD2 under orthostatic load, which is associated with the reaction of the autonomic nervous system, was revealed. Thus, the nature of the heart rate response to orthostatic load in athletes is determined by the level of stress of the body's regulatory systems.

Keywords: heart rate variability, orthostatic load, elite athletes, autonomic nervous system.

Introduction

One of the most important components of the functional state of the athlete's body is the system of autonomic regulation of the heart rate (Murakami et al., 2025; Laborde et al., 2024). There are many approaches to studying the nature of the reaction of the system of regulation of cardiointervals to the load (Mosley et al., 2024; Grégoire et al., 2025). But a more informative and safe method is the load with orthostatic changes (Gronwald et al., 2024). When moving from a horizontal to a vertical position, the blood flow to the right parts of the heart decreases, thereby reducing the minute blood volume. As a result, arterial pressure decreases, which is a strong irritant for the mechanoreceptors of various baroreflex zones. The first mechanism of maintaining arterial pressure corresponds to the mechanism of baroreflex regulation (da Fonseca et al., 2024).

Traditionally, heart rate variability indicates the adaptation responses to physical and mental stress (Di Credico et al., 2024). Some authors used heart rate variability estimates at different stages of sports activity: pre-start state (Botek et al., 2024), training and competition periods (Howard et al., 2024). Based on heart rate variability values, endurance intensity threshold levels were identified for athletes (Kaufmann et al., 2023). The correlation between heart rate variability and cortisol concentration was examined (Kayacan et al., 2021). Also, heart rate variability values were used to assess cardiorespiratory fitness in athletes during exercise (Mongin et al., 2022).

The modern approach to assessing the heart rate variability and the state of the autonomic nervous system is based on the standards proposed in 1996 at a joint meeting of the European Society of Cardiology and the North American Society of Electrical Pacing and Electrophysiology. According to these standards, heart rate variability is recommended to be measured by short (5-minute) or long (24-hour) recordings of cardiac intervals. It is recommended to analyze heart rate variability using statistical and spectral methods (Hamasaki et al., 2023).

The most common methods of variability analysis are the methods of rhythmocardiogram analysis. The analysis of the spectral characteristics of the rhythmocardiogram consists of three types of waves with different frequency characteristics: high-frequency oscillations (HF), low-frequency oscillations (LF) and very low frequency oscillations (VLF). High-frequency waves (HF) characterize the presence of significant periodic rhythm oscillations with a frequency of 0.15–0.40 Hz. Low-frequency oscillations (LF) reflect weakly expressed respiratory waves and the presence of waves with a frequency of 0.04 to 0.15 Hz. Very low frequency oscillations (VLF) characterize the absence of the above-described periodicity and long-period waves. Spectral analysis of the heart rhythm allows us to identify periodic components in heart rhythm oscillations and quantitatively assess their contribution to the rhythm dynamics. The area of the spectrum curve corresponding to the frequency range is most often estimated - the power within a certain frequency range (in ms^2).

The results of spectral analysis are usually presented in the form of a frequency distribution graph, which can easily be used to judge the balance of activation of the autonomic nervous system.

But, asses of functional state of the human body as a whole by active orthostatic test provide importance information.

Among different parameters of variability of heart rate which registered during orthostatic load is spectral analysis of cardio intervals and scatter plot analysis (Pham et al., 2021; Kimura et al., 2024). During analysis of orthostatic load needed consider of transition process of regulation of heart rate as non stationary processes.

Proceeding from this, non-parametric methods are used to analyze these processes, one of which is a skaterogram.

The aim of the work: study of the characteristics of the response of heart rate variability to orthostatic load in elite athletes.

Materials and Methods

The study involved 26 elite Greco-Roman wrestlers age (24.42; SD=2.52). All athletes had a high level of health and were cleared in accordance with the recommendations of the Ethical Standards of the Helsinki Declaration.

Procedure

Heart rate variability was studied according to the Recommendations of the European Association of Cardiology and the North American Association of Arrhythmology and Electrophysiology. The “Polar RS800CX” cardiac monitor was used to record the heart rate during active orthostatic load. The studies were conducted in two positions: horizontal (5 min heart rate recording) and vertical (5 min heart rate recording). Heart rate variability data were calculated using the “Kubios HRV” statistical program.

To analyze the non-stationary transient process of the heart rhythm regulation system, a non-parametric research method was used – scatterograms. The parameters SD1 (manifestation of aperiodic heart rhythm oscillations) and SD2 (slow heart rhythm oscillations) were determined.

Statistical Analysis

Statistical analysis was performed using the Statistica 12 software package. The sample of athletes did not correspond to the normal distribution, so the Wilcoxon nonparametric statistics was used. The median and the first (lower) quartile (25%), the third (upper) quartile (75%) and interquartile range (IQR) were determined accordingly.

Results

Based on our previous data, scales characterizing the heart rate response to orthostatic load were proposed: optimal, low stress, and overstrain (Korobeynikov et al., 2023). Table 1 presents a classification of the response of the autonomic heart rate regulation system to orthostatic load. One of the criteria indicating the heart rate response to orthostatic load is SDNN.

Table 1 Classification of the response of the autonomic regulation system of the heart rhythm to orthostatic load

Type of response	SDNN, ms
Optimal	≥ 75
Low stress	23-74
Overstrain	≤ 22

According to the authors, SDNN indicates the combined effect of both parts of the autonomic nervous system on the sinus node of the heart (Dorey et al., 2021).

Our analysis revealed that 34% of athletes have an optimal type of heart rate regulation response to orthostatic stress, 52% of athletes have low stress, and 14% of athletes have overstrain.

The analysis of heart rate variability indicators in athletes with different responses to orthostatic stress is presented in Table 2.

Table 2 Heart rate variability in athletes with different responses to orthostatic stress (Median, interquartile range (IQR), n=29)

Values	Type of response		
	Optimal	Low stress	Overstrain
horizontal position			
Mean NN, ms	920,45 (240,33)	910,17 (149,71)	750,57 (250,05)***
SDNN, ms	70,36 (11,09)	58,82 (22,89)*	30,72 (25,97)***
vertical position			
Mean NN, ms	790,53 (119,79)	720,38 (219,61)	692,18 (279,61)*
SDNN, ms	50,67 (19,44)	40,86 (29,99)	20,67 (19,96)*

Note:

* - $p < 0,05$, compared to a group of athletes with optimal response to orthostatic loading;

** - $p < 0,05$, compared to a group of athletes with low stress response to orthostatic loading.

The data in Table 2 show that the nature of the heart rate variability response to orthostatic load is associated with the level of stress of the regulatory systems. The results of the spectral analysis of the heart rate in the horizontal position in athletes with optimal and low stress are characterized by the predominance of LF oscillations (Table 3). This indicates the activation of the sympathetic tone of the autonomic nervous system.

The study showed that athletes with an overstrain reaction to orthostatic load have a predominance of VLF and LF due to the sympathetic effect on the sinus node of the heart (Table 3). This indicates the influence of central energy exchange mechanisms in the horizontal position. In the vertical position, LF oscillations predominate in athletes with optimal and low stress to orthostatic load (Table 3).

Table 3 Values of spectral analyses of heart rate in athletes with different reaction on orthostatic load (Median, interquartile range (IQR), n=29)

Values	Type of response		
	Optimal	Low stress	Overstrain
horizontal position			
VLF, ms ²	22,00 (32,00)	8,00 (18)*	8,00 (15,50)*
LF, ms ²	43,50 (48,00)	13,00 (5,00)*	4,00 (17)***
HF, ms ²	35,00 (21,00)	7,00 (14,00)*	2,00 (7,00)***
LF/HF	1,08 (0,63)	2,04 (1,74)	4,28 (6,63)*
vertical position			
VLF, ms ²	4,00 (12,00)	1,00 (20,00)*	0,50 (1,00)*
LF, ms ²	9,00 (10,00)	9,00 (39,00)	1,50 (11,00)***
HF, ms ²	2,50 (1,00)	1,00 (4,00)	1,00 (2,50)
LF/HF	3,87 (6,28)	5,43 (7,27)*	3,35 (2,90)**

Note:

* - $p < 0,05$, compared to a group of athletes with optimal response to orthostatic loading;

** - $p < 0,05$, compared to a group of athletes with low stress response to orthostatic loading.

However, athletes show an increase in HF oscillations of the heart rate. This indicates activation of the sympathetic tone of the autonomic nervous system. The predominance of the LF component of heart rate oscillations in athletes with an overstrain reaction to orthostatic load is associated with activation of the sympathetic influence. The values of the heart rate scattergram in athletes with different reactions to orthostatic load are presented in Table 4. The analyses showed a

tendency to decrease in the SD1 and SD2 values in the horizontal position. In the horizontal position, a decrease in the SD1 and SD2 values was observed, which indicates a deterioration in the heart rate response to orthostatic load.

Table 4 Heart rate scattergram values in athletes with different responses to orthostatic stress (Median, interquartile range (IQR), n=29)

Values	Type of response		
	Optimal	Low stress	Overstrain
horizontal position			
SD1, mc ²	56,40 (4,83)	33,00 (32,9)*	16,35 (22,10)**
SD2, mc ²	113,90 (42,20)	79,40 (39,30)*	54,00 (19,60)***
vertical position			
SD1, mc ²	32,65 (13,90)	19,60 (10,70)*	10,50 (14,00)***
SD2, mc ²	100,45 (66,85)	64,70 (16,50)*	38,30 (23,80)***

Note:

* - $p < 0,05$, compared to a group of athletes with optimal response to orthostatic loading;

** - $p < 0,05$, compared to a group of athletes with low stress response to orthostatic loading.

Discussion

The study showed that elite athletes have different types of heart rate variability response to orthostatic load: optimal (34%), low stress (52%) and overstrain (14%). The results obtained correlate with the idea of about the different degrees of stress of the regulatory systems during the adaptation of the autonomic nervous system to physical load (Chernozub et al., 2024). Orthostatic load is a convenient model of the adaptation process for studying the transient process of heart rate fluctuations in athletes. The study shows the predominance of the sympathetic tone of the autonomic regulation of the heart rate in athletes with optimal and low stress response to orthostatic load. This is manifested by an increase in LF oscillations of cardiointervals.

In athletes with an overstrain reaction to orthostatic load, VLF and LF oscillations predominate, indicating the activation of central cortical regulation through sympathetic influences on the sinus node of the heart. At the same time, an increase in HF power was shown.

Some authors believe that LF power is not only an indicator of sympathetic influence, but also includes a parasympathetic component (Grant et al., 2009; Riganello et al., 2012). At the same time, the obtained results indicate the influence of central mechanisms of energy exchange when changing the position in orthostasis (Korobeynikov et al., 2016; Sempere et al., 2024)

Existing ideas about the analysis of scatter diagrams provide information on periodic (low) and aperiodic (random) oscillations of the heart rate (Dorey et al., 2021). The activity of periodic (low) oscillations of the heart rate indicates the longitudinal axis of the scattergram (SD2). Aperiodic (random) oscillations of the heart rate are present on the transverse axis of the scattergram (SD1). According to the physiological mechanisms linking cardiac oscillations, the SD1 parameter reflects sympathetic activity, and the SD2 parameter indicates parasympathetic activity in regulating the heart rhythm.

Conclusion

The nature of the heart rate response to orthostatic load in athletes is determined by the level of stress of the body's regulatory systems. Athletes with optimal and low stress of response to orthostatic load show a predominance of the LF power of heart rate variability. A tendency to decrease SD1 and SD2 under orthostatic load is revealed, which is associated with the reaction of the autonomic nervous system.

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